

Data Management Plan

version 1.0

WORK PACKAGE 2
DELIVERABLE 2.1

OB-VISLY

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 894215.

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OB-VISLY

**An Ontology-based Visual Analytics Approach to Big Data from
Agricultural Monitoring Infrastructure**

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May 19, 2021

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Abstract

Increasing challenges for agricultural production such as climate change, environmental concerns, energy demands, and growing expectations from consumers triggered the necessity for innovation using data-driven approaches such as visual analytics. OB-VISLY extends the visual analytics approach with a structural way of data organization (ontologies), data mining, and visualization techniques to retrieve knowledge from the agricultural monitoring data. The latest advances in data visualization and analytics made it possible to fully exploit the potential of the proposed approach and gain insights into high complexity datasets (multi-source, multi-scale, and different stages). In OB-VISLY, I will carry out state-of-the-art research that unites two strands of recent, significant inquiry: Big Data analytics in the agricultural sector and visual methods. OB-VISLY aims to (1) establish a regionally significant dataspace enabled to synthesize information about fruit-growing apple orchards and vineyards and derive insight from massive, dynamic, and often conflicting data by providing up-to-date, consistent, and credible assessments; (2) create a single visual analytics user interface that can turn the data into knowledge for users of different information retrieval proficiency. OB-VISLY will establish and implement an innovative visual analytics-enabled dataspace within the European agricultural sector. The findings will contribute to European priority in building a digital single market and tackle obstacles that hinder the exploitation of big data and digital tools. Thus OB-VISLY will serve social and environmental well-being by uncovering hidden patterns from big agricultural data for future sustainable and environmentally friendly development. Such an endeavor aims to pave a way towards strengthening precision and conservation agriculture methods and create an added value to sustain under competitive conditions and increase agricultural potential in Europe.

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Acronyms and Definitions

A

AI Artificial Intelligence. 7

D

DMP Data Management Plan. 1

G

GDPR General Data Protection Regulation. 11

GeoSPARQL A Geographic Query Language for RDF Data. 8

J

JSON JavaScript Object Notation. 5

JSON-LD JavaScript Object Notation for Linked Data. 5

O

OBDI Ontology-based Data Integration. 8

OB-VISLY An Ontology-based Visual Analytics Approach to Big Data from Agricultural Monitoring Infrastructure. 1

ontology A set of concepts and categories in a subject area or domain that shows their properties and the relations between them. 2

OWL W3C Web Ontology Language. 5

R

RDF Resource Description Framework. 5

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Introduction and context

OB-VISLY Data Management Plan (DMP) gives an overview of the data and services adopted within the project, enabling us to manage, re-use, and share the data with the scientific community and the wider public. Data management is the core concern of the OB-VISLY project, as it focuses on data harmonization, interoperability, and visualization.

FAIR data principles [1] are the driving force behind the project, and the current DMP outlines the core aspects addressed in “Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020.”

[1]: Wilkinson et al. (2016), ‘The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship’

0.1 Basic project information

Project name: An Ontology-based Visual Analytics Approach to Big Data from Agricultural Monitoring Infrastructure

Acronym: OB-VISLY

Funding body: This project has received funding from the European Union’s H2020-MSCA-IF-2019 under grant agreement No **894215**

Budget: € 171 473,28

Project start date: 5 October 2020

Duration: 24 months

Secondment: MISTEA, SupAgro, INRA, Montpellier, France

Partnering organization Laimburg Research, Free University of Bolzano, Wageningen R&D. Figure 0.1 represents the interdisciplinary nature of the project and involvement of partners with various expertise.

Figure 0.1: Interdisciplinary partners within OB-VISLY project

0.2 Project objectives

OB-VISLY aims to build a human-centered approach to Big Data acquired from agricultural monitoring (in particular apple orchards and vineyards) by developing ontology-based visual analytics. OB-VISLY will be designed as an interactive visual analytics system enabled to answer "what" and "why" about fruit-growing activities. Thus, the system will go beyond the traditional ways of

organizing data by creating a data space to explore and get insight. The main objectives are:

- O1.** To establish a regionally important data space enabled to (a) synthesize information about fruit-growing apple orchards and vineyards and (b) derive insight from massive, dynamic, and often conflicting data by providing up-to-date, consistent, and credible assessments from agricultural monitoring data.
- O2.** To create (a) a single visual analytics user interface that can (b) turn the data into knowledge for users of different information retrieval proficiency.

OB-VISLY extends the visual analytics approach with a structural way of data organization (ontology), data mining, and visualization techniques to retrieve knowledge from the agricultural monitoring data. Furthermore, the latest advances in data visualization and analytics made it possible to fully exploit the potential of the proposed approach and gain insights into high complexity datasets (multi-source, multi-scale, and different stages).

OB-VISLY aims at applying cross-disciplinary methods in collaboration with regional (Laimburg Research, UniBZ) and international partners (MISTEA Montpellier SupAgro, INRA (secondment); Wageningen U&R).

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DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

Data Summary

1

1.1 Objectives

OB-VISLY aims at "creating a comprehensive strategy, which can enable domain experts that often lack information retrieval proficiency to acquire knowledge from high complexity datasets (multi-source, multi-scale, and different stages, etc.)." To establish an adequate data-driven approach, we adopt semantic data technology and advanced visualization techniques.

Data-driven applications require the development of visualization tools to aid analytical reasoning, improving our understanding of data. OB-VISLY extends the visual analytics approach with a structural way of data organization through ontologies, data mining, and visualization techniques to retrieve knowledge from the agricultural data (e.g., apple variety testing).

1.2 Research data description

OB-VISLY works with existing data sets, and it aims to generate new knowledge from available information by designing an ontology-driven framework for data analysis and visualization.

- ▶ Apple variety testing Based on the mutually signed data usage agreement with the Laimburg Research Center (Laimburg, Italy), OB-VISLY utilizes the data about the apple variety testing program. This variety testing program runs in South Tyrol for more than 20 years and aims at documenting the performance of various apple varieties and provide farming recommendations for apple growers. The dataset consists of varieties description, information about annual harvest, storage conditions, and orchard characteristics.
- ▶ Climate data includes:
 - Daily values for temperature and precipitation
 - Monthly temperature values
 - Monthly precipitation values
 - Highest precipitation intensities (15 minutes to 24 hours)
 - Highest precipitation intensities (1 to 5 days)

Over the project course, an ontology for apple variety data is developing and will become available for the scientific community working on apple phenotyping. The apple variety ontology covers various stages of the apple testing program, from planting to post-harvest characteristics.

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1.3 Data provenance

Project partner Laimburg Research provides the Apple Variety dataset, which is used according to the Data Usage Agreement mutually signed by EURAC Research and Laimburg Research on 07.01.2021. The apple variety dataset is collected by Laimburg Research for more than 20 years and describes the performance of varieties during their life-circle. This data is stored in a relational database accessed by authorized parties. In addition, climate data is collected by the province of Bolzano and distributed through the Alto-Adige Open Data portal.

1.4 Data formats and size

The data used in OB-VISLY comes from various forms, including structured database, geospatial vector, and raster data, and unstructured formats. OB-VISLY adopts further data formats:

- ▶ Structured data formats:
 - Relational database
 - Spreadsheets in structured format
 - JSON files
 - OWL
 - RDF, JSON-LD
- ▶ Unstructured data formats:
 - Domain knowledge collected through interviews and scientific discussions.

OB-VISLY aims to minimize the physical data storage and maximize the reuse of available data sources through designing an effective ontology-based data network.

1.5 Data utility

We identified several target groups and end-users who can directly benefit from the project outcomes:

- ▶ **AgriFood researchers** (scientific organizations working in the field of digital transformation in agriculture).
- ▶ **Fruit-growing consultants**
- ▶ **Data providers**

FAIR data

2

To ensure compatibility, within OB-VISLY, we adopt several FAIR data principles:

- ▶ To be findable: the metadata and data are accessed using unique and persistent identifiers and indexed through a searchable directory.
- ▶ To be accessible: the metadata is retrievable by its identifier through the open, free, and universally implementable protocol. The protocol allows public access following authentication and authorization procedure if necessary.
- ▶ To be interoperable: the metadata uses the formal, accessible, and common language of knowledge representation and gives credit to the external metadata and data.
- ▶ To be reusable: the metadata is published under accessible data usage license and includes provenance to satisfy domain-relevant community standards.

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 - Discoverability 6
 - Metadata standards 6
- 2.2 Making data openly accessible 7
- 2.3 Making data interoperable . . . 7
- 2.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences) 8

2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Discoverability

OB-VISLY adopts the FAIR data practices and the project outcomes are published when available and shared using unique and persistent identifiers and indexed through open access scientific platforms (GitLab, Zenodo, OpenAIRE):

- ▶ OpenAIRE (see Figure 2.1)
- ▶ Zenodo Open Access repository
- ▶ GitHub and GitLab
- ▶ EURAC metadata catalog

Metadata standards

Within OB-VISLY, we will apply standard procedures to create the metadata and help the scientific community identify and discover the information related to the project.

Project . 2020 - 2023 . On going

OB-VISLY

An Ontology-based Visual Analytics Approach to Big Data from Agricultural Monitoring Infrastructure

OPEN ACCESS MANDATE FOR PUBLICATIONS AND RESEARCH DATA

EUROPEAN COMMISSION

Funder: **European Commission** Project code: 894215 Call for proposal: H2020-MSCA-IF-2019
 Funded under: H2020 | MSCA-IF-EF-ST Overall Budget: 171,473 EUR Funder Contribution: 171,473 EUR
 Status: On going

Start Date	End Date
05 Oct 2020	05 Apr 2023

[Detailed project information \(CORDIS\) →](#)

LINK THIS PROJECT TO...

DEPOSIT YOUR RESEARCH

SHARE RESULTS

DOWNLOAD REPORT

Figure 2.1: OB-VISLY on OpenAIRE

2.2 Making data openly accessible

OB-VISLY is re-using the existing datasets and does not provide a physical replication of the data. However, OB-VISLY will acknowledge the open-access data. The apple variety testing dataset is used based on the Data Usage agreement, which does not allow to make the data publicly available. The ontological data description will be published open-access and become available for the broader scientific community.

2.3 Making data interoperable

OB-VISLY aims at making the project outcomes interoperable by designing an ontology-based application, where ontology enables mutual access to information about the system of interest and serves as a mediator of domain knowledge.

Data integration has become an essential part of information-processing applications in Artificial Intelligence (AI), databases, and data mining, where the importance of controlled semantics has become crucial. OB-VISLY implements an ontology-based data integration where each data element is semantically linked to a controlled and open-access vocabulary. The vocabulary defines the data independent from the information system and can be re-used by mapping the relationships between ontology and data. OB-VISLY adopts a conceptual and formal description, known as ontology, for formalizing a domain knowledge

about Apple Variety Testing Program. The Apple Variety Testing ontology describes concepts, relationships among them, employing a controlled vocabulary and allow logical assertions about the apple variety performance through time. Furthermore, we implement a framework for Ontology-based Data Integration (OBDI), which unites ontology, a set of data sources, by mapping relationships between them. Finally, OB-VISLY re-uses some of the existing schemas (e.g., Agri-Food Experiment Ontology, Ontology for Food Processing Experiments, GeoSPARQL, event ontology) to enrich the schema with information about apple orchards. The developed conceptual models will be published on an open-source platform and maintain using version control (GitLab, GitHub).

2.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)

OB-VISLY works with licensed data from Laimburg Research center under the Data Usage agreement and open access data. The licensed data will not be shared, but it will be used to design an ontological data description. This ontology will be published as open access and become available in Git and Zenodo. The open-access will allow for ontology will enable its re-use within the scientific community.

Allocations of resources

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3.1 Data Management cost assessment

3.1 Data Management cost assessment 9

OB-VISLY benefits from a series of open-access initiatives and services and aims to make project results comply with FAIR data principles. The costs associated with data publishing are a) maintenance of physical servers at the host institution and b) long-term data preservation. Thanks to Zenodo, long-term preservation is free and open for the scientific community. The GitLab and GitHub are used as the repositories for storing developing files.

Data security

4

4.1 Data security

4.1 Data security 10

OB-VISLY relies on the technical infrastructure available at the EURAC research and, in particular, the Center for Sensing Solutions. The advanced scientific infrastructure provides a secure data space available for authorized parties. In addition, all the information related to the project workflow is stored within a digitally and physically secured data center.

4.2 Data preservation 10

4.2 Data preservation

To ensure the long preservation of the project outcomes, the relevant data and code snippets will be uploaded to Zenodo and become accessible for a broader scientific community.

Ethical aspects

5

5.1 General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)

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 5.2 Sensitive data 11

OB-VISLY does not involve studies with genetic, biometric and/or health data. OB-VISLY meets legal and ethical requirements by ensuring that the project results respect all applicable EU and Italian laws, regulations, ethical principles, and values. Limited personal data (e.g., professional title, education level, gender, experience level) will be collected as a response to usability test about the final project outcome and processed based on consent of data subjects. The rights of data subjects will be protected in accordance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and in full compliance of the national data protection legislation in Italy (Legislative Decree no. 196 of 30.06.2003 as amended by Legislative Decree no.101 of 10.08.2018). The host institution, EURAC Research, takes all necessary measures to apply the GDPR that are in full compliance of the national data protection legislation in Italy (Legislative Decree no. 196 of 30.06.2003 as amended by Legislative Decree no.101 of 10.08.2018). A Data Protection Officer is appointed for the Project and their contact information is made available to data subjects in consent materials.

5.2 Sensitive data

OB-VISLY does not process any special categories of personal data. A limited personal data (e.g., professional experience, education level, gender, experience level) will be collected during interviewing with the stakeholders and project partners. Only limited personal data relevant for the project development will be collected and the data minimization principle will be applied. EURAC Research as the data controller ensures that the data collection, processing, and storage will comply with privacy statements within Regulation (EU) 2016/679, GDPR, and thus according to Article 13, the data subject will be informed about the processing of their personal data. OB-VISLY deals with environmental data either available under an open-source license and distributed through open access (weather data in South Tyrol), as well as data collected by the host institution and Laimburg Research and do not deal with sensitive personal data. The research data (extract from the database on Apple Variety Testing) is provided by the project partner, Laimburg Research under mutually signed Data usage agreement. The data usage agreement specifies the rights of both parties and entitles EURAC to process and disseminate the results of the data analysis within the project OB-VISLY. The research outcomes will present only relevant information to the project objectives.

Bibliography

Here are the references in citation order.

- [1] Mark D Wilkinson et al. 'The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship'. In: *Scientific data* 3.1 (2016), pp. 1–9 (cited on page 1).